

A NOTE ON PURE CHARCOAL FROM CANE SUGAR

BY T. M. OZA

Pure sugar charcoal is prepared by the method of King (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 843). It is found that a heating to 1000° or more is not necessary at any stage during the preparation and that a temperature of 500-550° is quite enough.

Charcoal was prepared from cane sugar by Shah (*ibid.*, 1929, 2664) for combustion in oxygen and oxides of nitrogen. His charcoal is reported to leave 0.12% ash on incineration. King (*loc. cit.*) has extended this method and obtained charcoal from centrifuged coffee-sugar which leaves no ash on incineration. The present author has applied the King's method of removing mineral matter to sugar charcoal, prepared by Shah's method, and found that the comparatively large amount of mineral matter (0.75% ash) in his charcoal is mostly eliminated in only one and completely eliminated in two of King's subsequent operations.

Large crystals of cane sugar were heated in a porcelain dish (Shah, *loc. cit.*) till the charcoal formed was brittle between fingers. This charcoal (about 50 g. each time) was then heated at 500° for 7 hours, in a *hyvac* vacuum, in a vertical tube provided with a ground glass joint and a tap at its top, the heating of the tube and pumping of the sweet smelling gases, again generated, being continued for more than two hours at a stretch; during the halt the charcoal was not allowed to be exposed to air. The charcoal was next heated in a current of chlorine at 500° (10 litres for 25 g.) after which it was again exhausted at 500° for two hours*. This charcoal contained adsorbed chlorine and on being incinerated gave the following results:

- I. 1.3280 g. charcoal left 0.0102 g. ash (0.77 %).
- II. 0.2386 g. charcoal left 0.0018 g. ash (0.75 %).

Through a layer of charcoal, thus obtained, hydrogen was passed for one hour at room temperature and then for one hour at 500°. It was then finely ground and treated in a platinum vessel with hydrofluoric acid to form a paste and digested on a small flame for half an hour, the treatment with hydrofluoric acid repeated, the charcoal dried and strongly heated and thrown into pure concentrated HCl and boiled for about one hour. After diluting with much water the contents of the beaker were filtered, the charcoal washed free of chloride, dried and exhausted at 500°. On incineration 0.8667 g. charcoal left 0.0006g. ash (i.e., 0.07%). Another treatment with HF etc. eliminated the mineral matter completely (two places of decimal).

The use of ash-free charcoal in finer studies with charcoal has been emphasised by Miller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1866). The author in his study on the action of charcoal on sodium nitrite *in vacuo* found that the charcoal before chlorine treatment reacted only violently at 265° and that the purer charcoal reacted at and above 300°, the reaction becoming violent only between 355° and 370° depending upon the purity of charcoal. The purer the charcoal, the slower was its reaction and the better was its reducing power.

KARNATAK COLLEGE,
DHARWAR.

Received November 1, 1943.

*This in Shah's method, is followed by treatment with nitric oxide and exhaustion at 1000°.